

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW GUIDE

Women in Leadership Positions in Technology: An Analysis of Lived Experiences

Sociodemographic Questions

Interviewee:

1. What is your age?
2. Which city do you live in? Which state?
3. Marital status?
4. Do you have children? If so, how many?
5. Do you live with anyone? If so, could you share with whom?
6. Which leadership position(s) do you currently hold or have you held??
7. In which technology sector(s) of the company?
8. What is the size of the team you lead?
9. What is the size of the company? (Small, Medium, Large)
10. How long have you been / were you in this position?

Education:

1. What is your level of education??
 2. Which course(s) did you complete?
 3. Why IT?
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Research Questions

1. What path/trajectory did you follow to become a leader?
2. What were the main challenges encountered along this path?
3. How did you overcome these challenges?
4. In a leadership position, are these challenges the same?
5. What influenced/motivated you to pursue a leadership position?